

The Coupling Constants Series and the Hadronic Structure - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the new 8T, and in particular the proof of the arbitrary variations term to vanish into fermions, alongside the Bosons as net curvature on the manifold, it is possible to expand the idea of Hadronic structure. In particular it becomes clear that the majority of the energy of the structure is depended upon the curve itself, which is the sea of Gluons. There could be virtual curvatures as well.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. The following is the original proof from the 8T thesis; notice that M is now the matric tensor, g is the Ricci flow, which was the result of parametrizing the manifold to "s" variable.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

Equation reads, length to manifold, manifold to matric, matric to flow, flow to time. δg As amount of arbitrary variations, which by demands of stationarity we require to vanish. Discretizing and partitioning the term δg into a series of sub elements, we can derive the existence of fermions, i.e. showing that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

Given four elements distinct:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 > 0$$

$$\delta g_3 + \delta g_4 < 0$$

If

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 + \delta g_4 \neq 0$$

Than the overall series cannot vanish, by that logic we need even amounts of equal elements of pluses and minuses. The amount must be even and summed as zero, ensuring stationary Lorentz manifold. Suppose that we had three distinct elements, two pluses and minus:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 > 0$$

or

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 < 0$$

Demanding the series to vanish this will exclude this result, and so there could not be three distinct elements in the series, else the overall series will not vanish to zero.

As a result of those sceneries, we require the series to have an even amount of variation elements, manifesting as two distinct elements in the series, which differ in sign. If we allow those sub elements in the series to vary as well, and by the above reasoning, there are only two elements in the series, they are varying in a discrete way, or forming a group. Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature

$$O: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination. $\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$ For example. Even though the sub elements in the series are varying, the overall series can vanish. Now, count all the ways of possible combinations of those elements. We are going to analyze by the integral signs. Since it is a group, there is a natural map, which change an element to itself. One built his analysis firstly on those natural maps. So:

$$(1(e)1(e)1)$$

$$2(e)2(e)2$$

$$(221)$$

$$(112)$$

$$(211)$$

$$(122)$$

$$(212)$$

$$(121)$$

It is possible to construct the visualization of the hadron structure as the following illustration, as presented in the 8T thesis and in previous papers:

That is the original proof from the 8T thesis. From here on out we have a completely new paper. Since the hadron is a composite of just three arbitrary variations known as Quarks, and a sea of Gluons, in which increase the probability of arrival for another gluon as it is a net curvature on the manifold, denoted by equations (1.45) and (1.46). equation is meant that the net curvature is the summation over a segment of the matric tensor.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.45)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i = \int_{M_\mu}^{M_\nu} N_V dM \quad (1.46)$$

From that point of view, the hadron structure is more complex than just bound state of two varying elements forming a threefold combination. The sea of Gluons must be taken into account. Despite the fact that they are massless, their energy is contributing to the proton overall energy, and eventually to its mass. That is by the famous equation of Albert Einstein. Since the majority of the Proton is constructed by the Gluon sea, so does the majority of the Proton mass. If the sea of Gluons is finite in size, so does the mass of the Proton. If the sea of Gluons is increasing in size, so does the energy of the proton, and eventually it's mass. The configuration of the Quark triplet and the sea of gluons can, similar to QFT, added orthogonal curvatures, which vanish and can be regarded as Quarks and anti Quarks pairs

$$\langle \delta g_i | -\delta g_i \rangle = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

That is due to the symmetry of the primorial under sign reversal, allowing anti-matter into our framework:

$$\left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \left[-2N_3 - \frac{1}{2} \right] - \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.51)$$

$$\langle +3_i | -3_i \rangle = 0$$

$$\langle \gamma_i | \gamma_i^- \rangle = 0$$

So according to those ideas, the hadron energy and mass is composed mainly by the energy of the sea of Gluons. Contributions are made using matter and anti-matter pairs; Both bosonic and fermionic, nature is invariant. Since they are vanishing, each zero added to the mass term of the proton can be thought as a vanishing pair of certain sort. The vanishing pairs in the 8T are orthogonal curvatures, with inner product zero. The actual triplet of quarks than are contributing in a insignificant amount compared with the bosonic Gluon sea and the orthogonal curvatures.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)